

Historical Case Studies (D3.3)

115966 – PREFER

**Patient Preferences in
Benefit-Risk Assessments
during the Drug Life Cycle**

**WP3 – Historical Case
Studies**

Lead contributor	Leo Russo (23–Pfizer)
	Leo.j.russo@pfizer.com
Other contributors	Haley Kaplowitz, Christine A Radawski, JuAn Wang, Ian Smith, Cecilia Jimenez Moreno, Isabelle Huys, Tarek Hammad, Byron Jones, Filip Mussen, Dasha Cherepanov, Marie Falahee, Gwenda Simons, George Quartey, Andreas Brueckner

Due date	
Delivery date	November 22 nd , 2021
Deliverable type	
Dissemination level	PU

Document History

Version	Date	Description
V1.0	November 22 nd , 2021	Draft Version
V2.0	February 7 th , 2022	Final Version

Information within this report that may influence other PREFER tasks

Linked task	Points from this report that are of particular relevance to the linked task
Task 4.2 Preparation of organizational requirements and best practices for conducting of case studies	Lessons learned from interviews of lead investigators were reviewed to inform WP3 Case Study Designs.
Task 4.4 Creating recommendations in consultation with stakeholder advisory groups (Citing Case Studies as examples for Final Recommendations.
WP2 (Task 2.1) and Case Study Leads.	Findings contribute to report of “Lessons Learned” for WP2.

Background

Industry and Academic partners who have previously conducted preference studies among patients may hold valuable data that are pertinent to the PREFER objectives. Task 3.3 involved the collection and review of historical case studies submitted by PREFER consortium members as a convenience sample of high-quality preference studies that could be used to supplement the prospective case studies in terms of possibly addressing PREFER methodological research questions and providing lessons learned that could inform the WP4 final recommendations.

Historical case studies of partners were evaluated in terms of their value in:

- 1) Contributing to one or more of our research questions
- 2) Providing lessons learned for conducting patient preference studies
- 3) Serving as example for the translation of our prospective case study results to other disease areas.

Methods

Data Collection - Wave 1

A team of 14 consortium members sought submissions, reviewed all submitted studies, and mapped them to PREFER methodological research questions. The first call for case studies in 2016 and 2017 resulted in **24** case studies that were all mapped to at least one PREFER methodological research question and most mapped to more than one. Refer to the PREFER Historical Case Studies Database in Appendix 2 for this mapping.

The 24 submitted studies for Wave 1 are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Historical Case Studies submitted in Wave 1 of Task 3.3

PREFER Partner	Title
Eli Lilly	Patients' Benefit-Risk Tradeoff Preferences for Psoriasis Treatment Attributes
Pfizer	Societal Preferences for rheumatoid arthritis treatments: evidence from a discrete choice experiment
Janssen	Relative importance of benefits and risks associated with antithrombotic therapies for acute coronary syndrome: patient and physician perspectives
Bayer	Patient Benefit-Risk Tradeoffs for Radioactive Iodine-Refractory Differentiated Thyroid Cancer Treatments
Universitätsklinikum Erlangen	Identifying factors of patient-preference for the treatment of rheumatoid arthritis with biologicals
UMC Utrecht and the Dutch Institute for Public Health	Parental preferences with regard to rotavirus vaccination for their newborn.
Novartis	Preferences and Stated Adherence for Antibiotic Treatment of Cystic Fibrosis Pseudomonas Infections
University of Birmingham	Preferences and acceptabilities in relation to drug formulations in paediatric populations
Janssen	Patients' Preferences Related to Benefits, Risks, and Formulations of Schizophrenia Treatment
Janssen	Physician benefit-risk preferences from two randomized long-acting injectable antipsychotic trials
Pfizer	The Effect of Information on Preferences for Treatments of Metastatic Renal Cell Carcinoma
AbbVie	Endometriosis Patient Preference Study
Janssen	Physician and patient benefit-risk preferences from two randomized long-acting injectable antipsychotic trials
Erasmus MC	Future pandemics and vaccination: Public opinion and attitudes across three European countries
Pfizer	Chronic Pain Patients' Treatment Preferences
Janssen	Patient Benefit-Risk Preferences for Anticoagulation and Antiplatelet Therapies in Atrial Fibrillation and Venous Thromboembolism
Janssen	Psychiatrists' Judgments About Antipsychotic Benefit and Risk Outcomes and Formulation in Schizophrenia Treatment
IEO European Institute of Oncology	Health Orientation, Knowledge, and Attitudes toward Genetic Testing and Personalized Genomic Services
University of Birmingham	Palatability and acceptability of multiparticulate (placebo) formulations: adults vs. children comparison
Janssen	Physician Benefit-Risk Preferences for Anticoagulation and Antiplatelet Therapies in Atrial Fibrillation and Venous Thromboembolism
Janssen	How Heterogeneous Are Preferences for Delaying Onset of Alzheimer's Disease? It Depends on How You Look
KU Leuven	Quantifying benefit-risk preferences for new medicines in rare disease patients and caregivers
IEO European Institute of Oncology	Direct to consumer genetic testing: Exploring psychological profile, health-related decisions and behaviors of consumers
Roche	Patients' and Physicians' Quantitative Benefit-Risk Preferences in Rheumatoid Arthritis

A data abstraction form was created and is contained in Appendix 1 of this report. In addition to the completed intake form, final study reports or publications were submitted for each case study.

During intake, lead investigators were interviewed and asked these direct questions:

1. How did you choose your final study design?
2. What were the key challenges in getting the study initiated?
3. How was the study funded?
4. How did you select the attributes and levels
5. Did the study have the impact you expected? If not, why do you think so?
6. How subjects recruited and what were the associated challenges?
7. Were study results shared with regulators or HTA bodies?
8. What was the unique contribution(s) of your study to this knowledge area?
9. Were your results used as part of a multi-criteria decision-making exercise?
10. Are there any aspects of the study that you consider new or novel?
11. If this is in support of a pharmaceutical product, what stage of development was that product in when the study was initiated?

All case studies were reviewed in their entirety, and five key items were recorded from each of the 26 studies (refer to the PREFER Historical Case Studies Database in Appendix 2):

1. PREFER Methodological Questions addressed (Column J)
2. Research Questions of this Study (Column K)
3. Medical Product Development Phase (Column L)
4. Regulator or HTA submission (Column M)
5. Investigators Lessons Learned (Column O)

Data Collection - Wave 2

Because of the response and success of the 1st call for case studies, the Task 3.3 team and Steering Committee decided that a second targeted call for case studies should be made, focused on specific gaps in the current PREFER portfolio of core and historical case studies. The second call for case studies was made in October 2019.

Here are the criteria given for the second call for historical case studies:

- Used one of these methods (i.e., non-DCE):
 - best-worst scaling type 1, 2 or 3; adaptive conjoint analysis; probabilistic threshold technique.
 - standard gamble; time tradeoff; swing weighting; visual analogue scale; and analytical hierarchy process.
- Conducted in a rare disease population.
- Was submitted to a regulatory agency or HTA body
- Conducted in the same disease population as one of the core case studies (RA, Lung Cancer, NMD)
- Utilized educational materials
- Conducted in an Eastern European country.

The second wave yielded **7** additional case studies. These were evaluated and categorized in the same manner as the 24 from Wave 1.

Results

All Historical Case Studies were mapped to PREFER Methodological Questions (see Column J of the PREFER Historical Case Studies Database in Appendix 2). Table 2 contains the number of mappings by each Methodological Question. If a PREFER Methodological Question is not listed, then it did not map to any of the historical case studies.

Table 2. PREFER research questions by # of mappings

Question	Historical Case Study Mappings
9b How generalizable are preferences from one specific population in a disease to different populations in that or related diseases?	6
11a To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Characteristics of patients	6
11b To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Stakeholder: patient vs caregiver vs physician	4
8a Do patients overemphasize benefits compared to harms?	4
2e To what degree do small changes in the number, type and definitions of attributes impact results for a given method?	3
2d How similar are the results from different methods applied with the same set of attributes on the same population?	3
4a1 Which presentation formats and combination of formats leads to the most consistent outcomes? (and thereby best understanding by respondents). Ex: By use of different versions of the same quantitative survey	3
4a3 Are the results of these format questions consistent in different patient populations and disease areas?	2
15b2 What is the impact of including attributes related to the disease/quality of life/price/... on the preferences elicited?	2
2c To what degree does repeat application of a method on different samples from the same population give similar results ?	1
4b1 What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks?	1
5b2 Can qualitative interviews provide sufficient information to assess these properties for method selection?	1
2d1 How similar are the results of simpler / faster / cheaper methods vs. more rigorous / in depth / expensive methods? (ex: threshold technique of a few attributes vs. DCE; ex: swing weighting vs. DCE or AHP)	0

PREFER Historical Case Studies Database

A digital and searchable database was created to archive the final historical case studies. A keyword search within "PREFER Methodological Questions addressed" was created so that WP4 users could identify case studies based upon concepts and terms in the Methodological Questions. A screenshot of the interface is shown below. "PREFER Historical Case Studies Database" is contained on Project Place in the WP3/Task 3.3 folder and is also contained in Appendix 2 of this report.

PREFER Historical Case Studies Database									
<small>HELP: Please click on the arrow on the Header of all columns for the ability to filter the values and narrow the records down by that column. Eg: To retrieve records with Country (s) is USA - click the arrow under Country (s) Header, below the Search bar in the pop up, select USA. For Keyword search within "PREFER Methodological Questions addressed", please use the pastel orange cell to enter your keyword. The records with that value will be highlighted in the excel.</small>									
<input type="text" value="Enter keyword to SEARCH ->"/> <input type="text" value="PREFER Methodological Qs addressed"/>									
Task 3.3 Reviewer	PREFER Partner	Title	Study Design	Disease Population	Year conducted	Study Size	Country(s)	PREFER Methodological Questions addressed	Research Questions of this Study
Leo Russo	Eli Lilly	Patients' Benefit/Risk Tradeoff Preferences for Psoriasis Treatment Attributes	DCE	Psoriasis Patients	2015		USA	26 To what degree do small changes in the number, type and definitions of attributes impact results for a given method? (respondents were given the same set of choice tasks (i.e. with the same levels), but the area of the body affected was changed. MAR estimates were higher when the face was the hypothesized area affected.)	(1) The primary objective of this study was to assess patients' tolerance for risks of therapies that could be nearly or entirely clear even small areas of psoriasis plaques of varying severity. (2) The study also evaluated the relative importance of different dosing schedules compared to therapeutic risks and improvements in efficacy.
Tarek Hammad	Pfizer	Societal Preferences for rheumatoid arthritis treatments: evidence from a discrete choice experiment	DCE	Rheumatoid arthritis	2014	733	Canada	11a To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Characteristics of patients	Determine the value society places on aspects of RA treatment
Leo Russo	Janssen	Relative importance of benefits and risks associated with antithrombotic therapies for acute coronary syndrome: patient and physician perspectives	BWS	Acute coronary syndrome (ACS)	2011-12	Patients (n=206), Physicians (n=273)	USA	11b To what degree do preference results in a disease vary with Stakeholder: patient vs caregiver vs physician. (study contained patient and physician samples) 481 What tests assess whether patients can perform a given set of cognitive tasks? (a face validity test is described on page 1736)	Quantify the US patients, and physicians perspective for health outcomes associated with antithrombotic therapies in acute coronary syndrome

Discussion

The historical case studies were valuable as resource to the Task 3.3 team who were also involved in design the PREFER case studies. Several commented on the examples as a good tool for them to consider all aspects of design. WP 4 task teams considered the investigator lessons learned (see column O of the PREFER Historical Case Studies Database in Appendix 2) carefully for the PREFER Qualification and Recommendations. In addition, recommendations with respect to interactions with patients, regulators and HTA bodies / reimbursement agencies have been developed. The PREFER "Points to consider for Method selection" also cover experience from the historical case studies.

The a priori objective of using the historical case studies for the translation of our prospective case study results to other disease areas was not realized and this may have been due to a lack of concordance in the design of these two sets of studies.

Conclusion

Use of the PREFER consortium members as a resource for high-quality patient preference studies and PREFER Recommendations was a success and resulted in 31 patient preference studies that were evaluated thoroughly and mapped to PREFER methodological questions and other relevant questions for the study design.

Appendix 1 - Data Abstraction Form

Historical Case Studies for PREFER - Information of Interest

Part 1 Obtained through review and extraction of submitted documents (e.g. protocol, publication(s), study instrument, final reports)

Characteristic	Entry	Additional Notes/Comments
Study Title		
Principal investigator		
Year the study was conducted		
Disease(s) under Study (including phase of disease)		
Patients <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number in study • Type /population • Age range 		
Peer-reviewed publications		
Study Design (e.g., CA, DCE, BWS)		
Research Questions		
Are you willing to share a copy of the Survey Instrument?		
Matched to which PREFER Research Question? *		
Country/Region studied		
Attributes and Levels/Favourable & Unfavourable Effects		
Analytical techniques used (e.g. representations of frequencies or severities, latent-class analysis etc.)		
If multi-country / multi-institution study, list collaborators		
Possibility to share patient level data for new analysis?		

Supportive qualitative research conducted		
Administration of Survey (interviewer-based, online panel, self-complete, etc)		
Validity tests?		
Output /Results (willingness to trade, odds ratio, probabilities, etc)		
Software used (for design and analysis of study)		
Sensitivity analysis conducted?		
Presence of Preference heterogeneity		
Generalizability?		
Response Rate?		
Reminders Used?		
Design aspects related to uncertainty?		

Part 2. Obtained through personal interview with one or more of the study investigators (30 min max)

1. How did you choose your final study design?
2. What were the key challenges in getting the study initiated?
3. How was the study funded?
4. How did you select the attributes and levels?
5. Did the study have the impact you expected? If not, why do you think so?
6. How subjects recruited and what were the associated challenges?
7. Were study results shared with regulators or HTA bodies?
8. What was the unique contribution(s) of your study to this knowledge area?
9. Were your results used as part of a multi-criteria decision-making exercise?
10. Are there any aspects of the study that you consider new or novel?
11. If this is in support of a pharmaceutical product, what stage of development was that product in when the study was initiated?

Appendix 2 - PREFER Historical Case Studies Database

